

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN SOLVING SPIRITUAL AND ETHICAL ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

We all know that the XXI century has entered history under the name of the age of information technology. Information and communication technologies have begun to affect all aspects of our lives. While in many areas the work has been efficient and effective, in some areas it has resulted in time savings, clear and fast targeting. Today, we cannot imagine our lives without information and communication technologies.

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As a result of comprehensive reforms and creative work carried out in our country, the consciousness and worldview of our people are changing. The importance of the vital idea of "From national revival to national progress" in building a state governed by the rule of law and civil society in our country is growing[1].

In order to turn a healthy outlook and creativity into a nationwide movement, to ensure the continuity of spiritual education in the family, educational institutions and

communities by widely promoting the idea of "From national revival to national progress" based on the principles of goodness and humanity in spirituality, which is becoming a top priority in society today. consists of regular organization.

Organization of propaganda and educational work on a scientific basis, increase the effectiveness of scientific and methodological research in the field, the introduction of a system of continuous monitoring aimed at strengthening the stability of the socio-spiritual environment, indifference to the fate of the people, localism, tribalism, corruption, family values It is necessary to take comprehensive measures to eliminate such evils as negligence and irresponsibility in the education of young people, to improve the culture of the population's use of the Internet.

A model for the introduction of information and communication

technologies in the system of spiritual and moral education in all educational institutions has been developed and is being used effectively. The introduction of information and communication technologies should be carried out in the field of organizational and practical, educational, advocacy.

Today, modern pedagogical technologies are widely used by professors in the educational process to train, educate and follow the world-class specialists. In particular, examples of teaching methods such as presentation, cluster, pinboard, insert, case-study can be cited. In particular, demonstrating the effectiveness of pedagogical activity through teaching (two levels of mastery) is called didactic description. The level of mastery is the level of mastering the content of teaching, which is a measure of the activity in mastering the content of teaching and the mastery of educational material[2].

Directions and forms of introduction of information and communication technologies have been developed in accordance with each area of activity. The introduction of information and communication technologies in the field of organizational and practical activities is expedient if it is carried out as follows:

First of all, it is necessary to create a unified information environment, depending on which industry they represent. Because it serves to have enough information in their field, and the listener becomes interested in their field. In such conditions, the formation of a methodological environment also gives good results. The applicant will need methodological assistance in any situation.

It is necessary to create a database for the recipient.

Organizing meaningful leisure time for students also helps to increase the effectiveness of spiritual work. In some cases, various clubs and spiritual and educational events are held in educational institutions. And young people get bored of this, and then they lose interest.

If the activities of the clubs are interesting and attractive through modern technologies, if the spiritual and educational activities are beautifully organized, then we will have one of the most effective ways to organize meaningful leisure time for young people. Another way to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work is to work with various public organizations. Whether there will be roundtables or other events at this time - all this will be of interest to young people, as well as the basis for the correctness of the explanatory work. For example, an educator may be a master of his or her field, but he or she may not have as much knowledge as other representatives of the field to find a solution to a problem. In this case, public organizations responsible for their field can be a good helper. Now the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in each educational institution must be determined. This is necessary in determining the dynamics of the ongoing spiritual and educational work.

The organization of activities in the field of spirituality and enlightenment on the basis of the use of information and communication technologies serves to ensure efficiency.

The introduction of information and communication technologies in the field of

educational activities mainly serves to implement the educational, pedagogical and developmental functions of the sciences. Given the special importance of the social sciences and humanities in ensuring the spiritual maturity of the individual, the development of electronic resources on them, the improvement of educational and methodological support is a priority.

Also, today's demand is the use of new technologies in educational work, the implementation of technological support of information resource centers and rooms "Spirituality and Enlightenment", the organization of clubs, virtual competitions with extensive use of information and communication technologies.

Today, as the issue of building a third Renaissance in Uzbekistan is a top priority, today we must selflessly serve our intellectuals to bring up worthy successors to our ancestors Khorezmi, Beruni, Ibn Sino, Mirzo Ulugbek, Navoi and Babur.

In this regard, the spiritual and educational activities based on cooperation to ensure the continuity of spiritual education in the family, educational institutions and communities are important in educating future well-educated and mature people and spiritually mature youth who will make a worthy contribution to the development of independent Uzbekistan. In addition, the establishment of research writing on the solution of problematic issues in the field of spirituality also serves as an important tool in solving problems in the field. Carrying out scientific research in this area is one of our great tasks "[3].

Activities in this area serve to form ideological immunity and motivation in

young people based on the creation of a social, intellectual and creative environment.

The role of information and communication technologies in increasing the effectiveness of advocacy is significant. Their effectiveness will be ensured on the basis of ensuring an interesting, comprehensive conduct of activities that are widely used in spiritual and moral education. The opportunities of such technologies can be used to organize presentations and video conferences, create Web pages, conduct "Days of Spirituality".

With the introduction of information and communication technologies, the opportunities for popularizing the traditions and values of the educational institution, passing it down from generation to generation are expanding.

Today, the field of educational activity is characterized by the abundance and diversity of forms of introduction of information and communication technologies. Electronic teaching aids on social sciences and humanities, animated literature in electronic format, electronic simulators, educational computer programs, expert systems, website, portal, slides in electronic format, feature and documentary films, videos, stands serves for the effective organization of educational processes.

In today's era of globalization, as young people receive a variety of information from various media, the Internet, the telephone, etc., there is information in this information that not only has a positive effect on their minds, but also has a negative impact. Therefore, it would be expedient for each educator to pay special

attention not only to teaching in the process of teaching, but also to teaching in the process of teaching using various forms

of information and communication technologies listed above.

References

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work. Tashkent, March 26, 2021, No. PQ-5040
2. Bakunin M. Cheterye stadii obucheniya. Level of competence. –M.: 2017.
3. М.Ботиров. Spiritual Life Program. <https://uza.uz/uz/>
4. Ochilova Nigora Ruzimuratovna. Moral Threats in the Era of Globalism: The Main Goals and Directions. ISSN 2792-4017 (online), Published under Volume:1 Issue: 4 in September-2021 Copyright (c) 2021 Author (s). This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY). To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
5. N. Ochilova. THE MAIN FEATURES OF WESTERN EUROPE MEDIEVAL, MODERN PHILOSOPHY AND PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS IN THE 9TH-12TH CENTURIES IN CENTRAL ASIA. Journal of Critical Reviews . ISSN- 2394-5125. Vol 7, Issue 14, 2020. 193-199. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.14.34>
6. N. Ochilova . East And West: Integration And Cooperation In The Process Of Globalization. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2020.2(11),543-546.